

hiTH-FOAM: A High-Fidelity Thermal-Hydraulics OpenFOAM-Based Package for Modeling Molten Salt Reactors

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ABSTRACT

In molten salt reactors, the flow of the liquid fuel affects the spatial distribution of precursors through the velocity field. Therefore, accurately capturing eddies in molten salt flow using Large Eddy Simulation (LES) can significantly alter the local precursor concentration. In this work, a comprehensive code package called *hiTH-FOAM* has been developed in OpenFOAM to model fluid flow using LES. For this purpose, the unresolved small-scale motions are modeled using a dynamic subgrid-scale (SGS) model developed for molten salt flows. Specifically, a dynamic model for the calculation of turbulent thermal diffusivity is developed to enhance the accuracy of thermal field predictions for molten salts with high Prandtl numbers. Since the molten salt has high temperatures in these reactors, thermal radiation effects are included by solving the Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) using the SP_3 method and employing a novel boundary condition known as the Gray Marshak boundary condition. The dynamic SGS model was verified using Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) data, and the SP_3 radiation model was validated against Sandia Flame D experimental data. Then, *hiTH-FOAM* is coupled with diffusion and SP_3 neutron transport solvers and used to model the one-sixteenth 3D slice of the European MSFR geometry. The results show that although the LES model significantly influences the precursor concentration distribution, its effect on the effective multiplication factor is negligible under steady state. The precursor distributions become more uniform due to the higher predicted velocity and the presence of eddies near the cavity wall arc. In any case, the influence of the LES model and thermal radiation on safety parameters such as temperature cannot be ignored. The LES model predicts a maximum temperature that is about 25 °C higher than that predicted by the RANS model.

Keywords: Large Eddy Simulation (LES), Thermal Radiation, Precursor distribution, Dynamic Subgrid-Scale model, Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs)

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Molten Salt Fast Reactors (MSFRs) have attracted considerable research interest [1] because of their superior fuel cycle efficiency and inherent safety features [2]. In the conceptual design of these reactors, the absence of solid components within the core cavity enables unrestricted circulation of the molten salt fuel [3]. On the other hand, since precursor distributions depend on the local velocity field, it is necessary to accurately model the flow within the primary loop. In recent studies, solvers based on computational fluid dynamics (CFD) have been developed to calculate these fields. Cammi et al. were the first to propose a coupled neutronics (multi-group diffusion), fluid mechanics, and temperature model in COMSOL Multiphysics environment to simulate MSRs. In this work, Navier–Stokes equations are used with the turbulence treatment according to the RANS (Reynolds Averaged Navier–Stokes) scheme for thermal-hydraulics calculation [4]. Fiorina et al. implemented a multi-physics model using finite element discretization in COMSOL to simulate both steady-state and accidental transients of MSRs. In this work, turbulence was modeled with the standard $k-\varepsilon$ model and logarithmic wall functions [5]. Aufiero et al. developed a multi-physics computational model in OpenFOAM to perform transient analyses of non-moderated Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs). In this solver, turbulence is modeled using the RANS equations with the realizable $k-\varepsilon$ model for incompressible flows and standard wall functions. [6]. Tibergera et al. developed a novel multi-physics

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simulation tool using the Discontinuous Galerkin Finite Element Method (DG-FEM) to model both steady-state and transient behavior in MSR. In this work, the $k - \varepsilon$ model was modified to account for turbulence production due to buoyancy and reformulated in logarithmic form to ensure the positivity of turbulence quantities [7]. Cervi et al. implemented a multi-physics solver in OpenFOAM to account for fuel compressibility and the effects of local bubble distribution in MSR. In this study, the Lahey $k - \varepsilon$ model was modified to include the impact of the dispersed phase on turbulence [8]. Laureau et al. studied power stability in unmoderated molten salt reactors (MSRs), focusing on the turbulence-induced temperature fluctuations. To capture these effects, Detached Eddies Simulation (DES) is applied to obtain time-dependent temperature and reactivity fluctuations [9].

The review of the literature indicates that the $k - \varepsilon$ model has been the predominant choice for turbulence modeling in MSR. As a RANS model, the computational cost of the $k - \varepsilon$ model is low. However, RANS cannot resolve the smaller turbulence scales, which may influence the local precursor distribution. Furthermore, the thermal radiation phenomenon has not been considered in the developed multi-physics tools. Due to the high temperature of the molten salt in these reactors, thermal radiation affects the temperature distribution, especially in accidental scenarios involving the energy leakage of hot molten salt into the vessel environment [10].

In this work, a comprehensive code package, hi-fidelity thermal-hydraulic (*hiTH-FOAM*), is developed in OpenFOAM to model turbulence-induced velocity and temperature fluctuations, as well as thermal radiation phenomena in MSR. For this purpose, the Dynamic Turbulent Kinetic Energy (Dyn-TKE) method is implemented as a subgrid-scale (SGS) model for LES using the object-oriented C++ programming language. This model was verified using Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) data and compared with five SGS models for a wall-bounded molten salt channel flow [11]. For modeling thermal radiation, the Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) was solved using the third-order spherical harmonic expansion method (SP_3) and implemented together with the innovative Gray Marshak boundary condition in OpenFOAM. To assess the performance of the SP_3 library, it undergoes verification against an analytical solution and validation using experimental data from Sandia Flame D benchmark test case [12]. Dyn-TKE and SP_3 are integrated in *hiTH-FOAM* and used to model a one-sixteenth of the 3D MSFR geometry. This paper investigates the extent to which a high-fidelity model in thermal-hydraulic calculations influences the predicted velocity and temperature distributions. Additionally, the choice of turbulence model can influence the distribution of delayed neutron precursors and, consequently, the effective multiplication factor in MSR. While this work builds on the OpenFOAM solver previously developed at PoliMi [6], *hiTH-FOAM* is a distinct package focused on high-fidelity thermal-hydraulics simulations with LES and radiation, extending beyond MSFR modeling.

2. Mathematical methodology

2.1. Turbulence Model

The governing equations for LES are derived by applying a spatial filtering operation to the continuity, Navier–Stokes, and energy equations. For compressible flows, density-weighted (Favre) filtering ($\tilde{\phi}(x, t) = \frac{\rho\phi}{\bar{\rho}}$) is employed to account for variations in density [13]. In the LES formulation, the SGS Reynolds stress tensor, τ_{ij}^{SGS} , and the SGS heat flux, q_i^{SGS} emerge in the momentum and energy equations, respectively, as a consequence of the filtering process. These terms represent unresolved small-scale turbulent motions that must be modeled using SGS models. The values of τ_{ij}^{SGS} and q_i^{SGS} are determined according to the specific SGS model employed.

To capture non-local and history effects on the SGS stresses, the TKE model introduces a transport equation for the SGS kinetic energy, as expressed in Eq. (1). In this model, τ_{ij}^{SGS} and v^{SGS} are calculated using Eq. (2) and Eq. (3), respectively.

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho} k^{SGS}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j k^{SGS}) = -\tau_{ij}^{SGS} \tilde{\zeta}_{ij} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left((\mu^{SGS} + \mu) \frac{\partial k^{SGS}}{\partial x_j} \right) - \frac{C_\varepsilon \bar{\rho} k^{SGS 1.5}}{\Delta} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{ij}^{SGS} = -2 \frac{\mu^{SGS}}{\rho} \tilde{S}_{ij} + \frac{1}{3} \tau_{kk} \delta_{ij} = -2 \nu^{SGS} \tilde{S}_{ij} + \frac{2}{3} k^{SGS} \delta_{ij} \quad (2)$$

$$\nu^{SGS} = (C_s \bar{\Delta}) \sqrt{k^{SGS}} \quad (3)$$

The main concept of the Dyn-TKE method is to determine the model constant parameters (e.g., C_s , C_ϵ and Pr^{SGS}) using information from the smallest resolved scales. In the absence of established references for determining these coefficients in the turbulence modeling of molten salt fluids with volumetric heat generation, the calibration of model constants becomes challenging, influenced by factors such as flow behavior and the range of Reynolds numbers. The dynamic method introduces a second filter, a test filter, with width $\hat{\Delta}$ larger than the original filter Δ ($\hat{\Delta} = 2\Delta$) to locally calculate the coefficients. In the present method, C_s is calculated according to Eq. (4) [14].

$$C_s = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\mathcal{L}_{ij} \mathcal{M}_{ij}}{\mathcal{M}_{ij} \mathcal{M}_{ij}} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_{ij} = \bar{\rho} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_j} - \bar{\rho} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i} \widehat{\tilde{u}_j} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{ij} = \hat{\Delta} \left(\frac{1}{2} (\bar{\rho} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_i} - \bar{\rho} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \widehat{\tilde{S}_{ij}} \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, the constant C_ϵ is dynamically calculated using Eq. (7).

$$C_\epsilon = \frac{2\hat{\Delta}}{(\widehat{\tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_i} - \widehat{\tilde{u}_i} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i})^{\frac{3}{2}}} \left(\nu \left(\frac{\partial \widehat{\tilde{u}_i}}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \widehat{\tilde{u}_i}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \widehat{\tilde{u}_i}}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \widehat{\tilde{u}_i}}{\partial x_j} \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

In this work, Pr^{SGS} is also calculated locally using Dyn-TKE method. For this purpose, SGS thermal diffusivity ($\alpha^{SGS} = \frac{\nu^{SGS}}{Pr^{SGS}}$), used to calculate q_i^{SGS} , is obtained from Eq. (8) [15].

$$\alpha^{SGS} = (C_\Gamma \Delta^2) |\widehat{\tilde{S}_{ij}}| \quad (8)$$

where

$$C_\Gamma \Delta^2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\mathcal{L}'_i \mathcal{M}'_i}{\mathcal{M}'_i \mathcal{M}'_i} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathcal{L}'_i = \bar{\rho} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i \tilde{h}} - \bar{\rho} \widehat{\tilde{u}_i} \widehat{\tilde{h}} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathcal{M}'_i = \frac{\hat{\Delta}^2}{\Delta^2} \bar{\rho} \left| \widehat{\tilde{S}_{ij}} \right| \frac{\partial \widehat{\tilde{h}}}{\partial x_i} - \bar{\rho} \left| \widehat{\tilde{S}_{ij}} \right| \frac{\partial \widehat{\tilde{h}}}{\partial x_i} \quad (11)$$

2.2. Thermal Radiation Model

The quasi-steady Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) is a complex integral-differential equation characterized by five independent variables distributed over the spatial and angular domains. (Eq. (12)) [16].

$$\hat{s} \cdot \nabla_{\tau} I + I = (1 - \omega) I_b + \frac{\omega}{4\pi} \int_{4\pi} I(\hat{s}') \Phi(\hat{s}, \hat{s}') d\hat{\Omega} \quad (12)$$

This paper gives only the final governing equations of Sp_3 approximation (Eq. (13)) and its Marshak boundary conditions (Eq. (14)). Additional information is provided in Ref. [12]. The SP_3 approximation is valid when the optical thickness is sufficiently large. For the MSFR geometry with absorption coefficient $k = 11.22 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and characteristic length around 2 m, the optical thickness is approximately 22, which supports the diffusion-like behaviour required for Sp_3 accuracy. However, near boundaries and in optically thin regions, higher-order approximations or discrete ordinate methods may provide better accuracy.

$$\frac{1}{3} \nabla_{\tau} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_1} \nabla_{\tau} J_0 \right) = \alpha_0 (J_0 - \frac{2}{3} J_2 - I_b) \quad (13a)$$

$$\frac{3}{7} \nabla_{\tau} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_3} \nabla_{\tau} J_2 \right) = \left(\frac{5}{3} \alpha_2 - \frac{4}{3} \alpha_0 \right) J_2 - 2\alpha_0 (J_0 - I_b) \quad (13b)$$

$$\hat{n} \cdot \nabla_{\tau} J_0 = \frac{3\varepsilon}{4 - 2\varepsilon} J_0 - \frac{3\varepsilon}{(4 - 2\varepsilon)\pi} \sigma_{SB} T_w^4 - \frac{3\varepsilon}{16 - 8\varepsilon} J_0 \quad (14a)$$

$$\hat{n} \cdot \nabla_{\tau} J_2 = -\frac{7}{8} J_0 + \frac{7}{8\pi} \sigma_{SB} T_w^4 + \frac{7 - 7\varepsilon}{6\varepsilon} \nabla_{\tau} J_0 + \frac{49}{24} J_2 \quad (14b)$$

In the RTE, spatial coordinates have been scaled using the extinction coefficient to make them non-dimensional, i.e. $\nabla_{\tau} = \frac{1}{\beta} \nabla$. Also, the extinction coefficient is defined as $\beta = k + \sigma_s$, and ω represents the single scattering albedo and is defined as $\omega = \frac{\sigma_s}{k + \sigma_s} = \frac{\sigma_s}{\beta}$, where σ_s and k are the scattering and absorption coefficients, respectively.

The coupling between radiation and heat transfer is achieved by introducing the heat source term, expressed in Eq. (15), into the energy equation.

$$S_{rad} = S_{abs} - S_{emi} = kG - 4\varepsilon\sigma_{SB}T^4 \quad (15)$$

where $G = 4\pi \left[J_0 - \frac{2}{3} J_2 \right]$ is the incident radiation and σ_{SB} represents the Stefan Boltzmann constant.

This work assumes that the molten salt behaves as a gray medium, implying that its thermal radiative properties are independent of wavelength. Accordingly, a single-wavelength radiative transfer model is adopted. Aghili et al. studied the effects of temperature and wavelength on thermal radiation in molten salt flow [10]. It should also be noted that molten salt exhibits a low scattering coefficient; therefore, scattering effects can be neglected [17].

3. Case Study modeling

In this work, the Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR) developed within the framework of the European SAMOSAFER project is selected [18]. One-sixteenth of the 3D MSFR geometry was modeled and meshed using the SALOME software (Figure 1). A total of 954842 tetrahedral mesh elements are used, with local refinement applied near the walls. The average wall-normal nondimensional distance (y_{wall}^+) on the cavity arc is 26.3. In this study, the geometry is simplified to enhance mesh generation efficiency and ensure better numerical convergence. Therefore, constant temperature (923 K) and velocity ($2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) are imposed on the heat exchanger and pump, respectively.

Figure 1. Geometry and meshing of one-sixteenth of the MSFR.

Thermo-physical properties of $LiF(78\%) - ThF_4(22\%)$ molten salt are given in Table I. The power density is calculated using *msfrSP₃FOAM*, which was developed at *Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI)* [1]. This multi-physics solver models neutron transport by applying the SP₃ approximation.

Table I. Thermo-physical properties of fluoride molten salt.

Parameter	Value	Units
Density (ρ)	4147.29	($kg \cdot m^{-3}$)
Kinematic viscosity (ν)	2.71×10^{-6}	($m^2 \cdot s^{-1}$)
Expansion coefficient (β)	2.14×10^{-6}	(K^{-1})
Specific heat capacity (C_p)	1524.86	($J \cdot K^{-1} \cdot kg^{-1}$)
Thermal conductivity (K)	1.007645	($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)
Prandtl number (pr)	17.05	-
Absorption coefficient (k)	11.22	(m^{-1})
Emission coefficient (ϵ)	0.3	-

4. Results and discussion

In this section, the impact of using LES instead of RANS on thermal-hydraulic fields, such as velocity and temperature, and on neutronic parameters, including precursor distributions and the effective multiplication factor, is evaluated. Figure 2 compares the streamlines obtained from the LES and RANS models in the one-sixteenth slice of the MSFR. The results demonstrate that the LES model predicts higher molten salt velocities in the inlet and outlet of the core compared to the RANS model. Furthermore, the LES model, unlike the RANS model, successfully resolved eddies near the cavity arc and in the upper region of the central axis. Figure 3 shows the temperature fields predicted by the LES and RANS models. To ensure a consistent comparison, thermal radiation effects are accounted for in both models. The LES model predicts more hot points as a result of capturing eddies in the fluid flow.

Figure 2. Velocity streamlines from the LES (a) and RANS (b) models.

Figure 3. Temperature fields from the LES (a) and RANS (b) models.

The turbulence model can influence neutron calculations by altering the velocity field, which consequently affects the spatial distribution of precursor concentrations. Figures 4, 5, and 6 illustrate the precursor concentrations corresponding to groups 1, 5, and 8, respectively. The results show that the precursor distribution in the MSFR is more uniform in the LES model than in the RANS model. This is due to the higher predicted velocities in the inlet and outlet of the core, as well as the capability of the LES model to resolve local turbulent eddies, which enhance mixing and reduce the local accumulation of precursors. Consequently, it can impact both the effective multiplication factor and the effective delayed neutron fraction.

Figure 4. First-group precursor concentration from the LES (a) and RANS (b) models.

Figure 5. Fifth-group precursor concentration from the LES (a) and RANS (b) models.

Figure 6. Eighth-group precursor concentration from the LES (a) and RANS (b) models.

To assess the influence of the turbulence models on the effective multiplication factor, neutronic calculations were conducted with both diffusion and SP_3 transport solvers and the values are compared in Table II. The results show that the turbulence model has a greater effect on the diffusion than on the SP_3 , although the impact remains negligible in both methods.

Table II. MSFR effective multiplication factor predicted by different models.

Models	k_{eff}	Discrepancy in k_{eff}
Diff-RANS	0.9861479	+ 48 pcm
Diff-LES	0.9866155	
SP_3 - RANS	0.985537	- 13 pcm
SP_3 -LES	0.985409	

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces *hiTH-FOAM*, a high-fidelity thermal-hydraulics package developed in OpenFOAM to simulate MSR. It incorporates LES for turbulence modeling and includes thermal radiation in the energy equation. The LES solver routine employs the Dyn-TKE model in both the velocity and thermal fields to automatically compute the turbulence coefficients. In this work, the dynamic calculation of turbulent thermal diffusivity is implemented in OpenFOAM using the object-oriented C++ programming language. This is particularly important for molten salt flows, which are characterized by high Prandtl numbers. Additionally, thermal radiation is modeled by solving the RTE using the SP_3 method and applying a gray Marshak boundary condition. *hiTH-FOAM* has been verified using DNS data and validated against the Sandia Flame D experimental data, and it has subsequently been coupled with neutronic solvers, including both diffusion and SP_3 models. The LES model predicts a maximum molten salt velocity of 2.31 m/s, while the RANS model predicts 1.69 m/s. Furthermore, the LES model yields a maximum temperature that is 25°C higher than that of the RANS model, a difference that could be important for safety assessment. The results also indicate that using the LES model can alter the total neutron flux by up to 42.5% due to changes in the precursor distribution. However, at the center of the cavity, the change in maximum flux is only 0.1%. Therefore, k_{eff} shows only a small difference of 48 pcm. However, when the SP_3 solver is employed, the difference decreases to 13 pcm. Future research will focus on quantifying the effects of velocity and temperature fluctuations on local reactivity variations and the resulting potential for instability. Furthermore, the new package will be used to simulate and analyze accidental conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Aghili Nasr et al. "Enhancing multi-physics modeling in new-generation nuclear reactors using machine learning: Implementing Gaussian Process Regression for updating cross sections". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **224**. 111720 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2025.111720>.
- [2] M. Aghili Nasr et al. "Neutronic and fuel cycle performance analysis of fluoride and chloride fuels in Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR)". *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **413**. 112506 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2023.112506>.
- [3] M. Brovchenko et al. "Optimization of the pre-conceptual design of the MSFR". 1-69 (2013).
- [4] A. Cammi et al. "A multi-physics modelling approach to the dynamics of Molten Salt Reactors". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **38**. 1356-1372 (2011). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2011.01.037>.
- [5] C. Fiorina et al. "Modelling and analysis of the MSFR transient behaviour". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **64**. 485-498 (2014). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2013.08.003>.
- [6] M. Aufiero et al. "Development of an OpenFOAM model for the Molten Salt Fast Reactor transient analysis". *Chemical Engineering Science*, **111**. 390-401 (2014). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2014.03.003>.
- [7] M. Tibergera et al. "A multi-physics solver for liquid-fueled fast systems based on the discontinuous Galerkin FEM discretization". *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **127**. 103427 (2020). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2020.103427>.
- [8] E. Cervi et al. "Development of a multiphysics model for the study of fuel compressibility effects in the Molten Salt Fast Reactor". *Chemical Engineering Science*, **193**. 379-393 (2019). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2018.09.025>.
- [9] Laureau et al. "Unmoderated molten salt reactors design optimisation for power stability". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **177**, p.109265 (2022). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109265>.
- [10] M. Aghili Nasr et al. "Development of a High-Fidelity Radiative Heat Transfer Model for Assessing Thermal Radiation Influence in Molten Salt Reactors". In *Proceedings of the NURETH-21*. Busan, Korea (2025).
- [11] M. Aghili Nasr et al. "Assessment of Subgrid-Scale Models for Large-Eddy Simulation of Heat-Generating Compressible Molten Salt Flows" (2025). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5716283>.
- [12] M. Aghili Nasr et al. "Implementation of the SP3 Solver with Gray Boundary Conditions in OpenFOAM for Thermal Radiation Modeling: Application to Molten Salt Reactors". *Nuclear Technology*. 1-19 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295450.2025.2470015>.
- [13] R. Kumar et al. "A study of LES-SGS closure models applied to a square buoyant cavity. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*", **98**. 164-75 (2016). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2016.02.057>.
- [14] W. Kim. "A new dynamic one-equation subgrid-scale model for large eddy simulations". In *Proceedings of the 33rd aerospace sciences meeting and exhibit*. Reno, NV, USA (1995).
- [15] P. Kakka et al. "Assessment of subgrid-scale models for large-eddy simulation of a planar turbulent wall-jet with heat transfer". *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, **153**. 119593(2020). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2020.119593>.
- [16] M. Modest and S. Mazumder. *Radiative heat transfer*. Academic press (2021).
- [17] S. ZHANG and X. SUN, "Convective and Radiative Heat Transfer in Molten Salts," *Nucl. Technol.*, **206**, 11, 1721 (2020); <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295450.2020.1749481>.
- [18] EU-funded SAMOSAFER project, Horizon 2020. URL 10.3030/847527.